

Multiparametric comparison of mesenchymal stromal cells obtained from trabecular bone by using a novel isolation method with those obtained by iliac crest aspiration from the same subjects.

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Abstract Trabecular bone fragments from femoral heads are sometimes used as bone grafts and have been described as a source of mesenchymal progenitor cells. Nevertheless, mesenchymal stromal cells (MSC) from trabecular bone have not been directly compared with MSC obtained under standard conditions from iliac crest aspiration of the same patients. This is the ideal control to avoid inter-individual variation. We have obtained MSC by a novel method (grinding bone fragments with a bone mill without enzymatic digestion) from the femoral heads of 11 patients undergoing hip replacement surgery and compared them with MSC obtained by standard iliac crest aspiration of bone marrow from the same patients. We have shown that trabecular bone MSC obtained by mechanically fragmented femoral heads fulfil the immunophenotypic and multi-lineage (adipogenic, osteogenic and chondrogenic) differentiation criteria used to define MSC. We have also differentially compared cellular yields, growth kinetics, cell cycle assessment, and colony-forming unit-fibroblast content of MSC from both sources and conclude that these parameters do not significantly differ. Nevertheless, the finding of slight differences, such as a higher expression of the immature marker CD90, a lower expansion time through the different passages, and a higher percentage of cycling cells in the trabecular bone MSC, warrants further studies with the isolation method proposed here in order to gain further knowledge of the status of MSC in this setting.

Keywords Mesenchymal stromal cells, Femoral heads, Bone marrow, Cell culture, Human.

Introduction

Hip arthroplasty is one of the most common procedures in orthopedic surgery, its frequency doubling in the last decade (Kurtz et al. 2005). The removed femoral heads have been used as a source of bone graft, either in the same surgical procedure as an autologous graft or cryopreserved for future use (Farrell et al. 2005), although femoral heads are often discarded.

Mesenchymal stromal cells (MSC) can differentiate into most stromal cell types (including osteocytes, adipocytes, and chondrocytes), and therefore, great research interest is being shown with regard to their biology and therapeutic roles in chronic degenerative disorders (Pountos et al. 2006; Le Blanc and Pittenger 2005). Bone marrow (BM) obtained after standard iliac crest aspiration was the first source reported to contain MSC. Other promising sources of MSC have been described, including umbilical cord blood and adipose tissue (Kern et al. 2006). BM from trabecular bone

(e.g. from femoral heads or knee), mostly obtained from patients undergoing elective surgery for a number of orthopedic disorders, has been reported as another source of MSC (Sakaguchi et al. 2004; Tuli et al. 2003a, 2003b). In the preliminary reports, trabecular bone was digested with collagenase to obtain a good cellular yield (Tuli et al. 2003a), but the MSC obtained from this source were not directly compared with those obtained under standard conditions from the iliac crest of the same subjects. Such a comparison would be of great interest, since MSC obtained from trabecular bone of patients diagnosed with osteoarthritis or undergoing surgery after an osteoporotic hip fracture might be altered either primarily or as a consequence of the underlying disease and therefore might be different from the MSC obtained from iliac crest aspiration. In the present work, we have obtained, by using a new isolation protocol, MSC from mechanically fragmented femoral heads from 11 patients

undergoing hip arthroplasty for osteoarthritis and compared them with MSC obtained from iliac crest aspiration from the same subjects. In addition to flow cytometric immunophenotyping and multilineage differentiation (adipogenic, chondrogenic, and osteogenic) to fulfil the International Society for Cellular Therapy (ISCT) criteria for the definition of MSC (Dominici et al. 2006), we have compared cellular yields, growth kinetics, cell cycle assessment, and the colony-forming unit-fibroblast (CFU-F) content of MSC from both sources.

Materials and methods

Patients and samples

All the procedures specified below were approved by the Ethical Committee of the Hospital Universitario de Salamanca and were also in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, as revised in 2000. Informed consent was obtained from all subjects included in the study.

Femoral heads were obtained from 11 patients who had undergone a partial hip arthroplasty in our institution as a treatment for osteoarthritis. During the surgical procedure, 5–10 ml BM was obtained by iliac crest aspiration. The median age was 72.5 years (range: 57–79 years), and the male/female ratio was 7/4.

MSC isolation and expansion

Once removed, the femoral heads were cut into several pieces with the help of a power saw (Striker Iberica, Madrid, Spain). Then, in the sterile environment within the operating room, bone fragments were ground by using a bone mill (Aesculap GB40; Aesculap, Tuttlingen, Germany), and the trabecular bone chips (≤ 5 mm in diameter) were placed into a sterile container with saline and taken to the laboratory. Subsequently, cells were diluted in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) filtered through a 40- μ m pore filter (Becton-Dickinson Biosciences [BDB], San Jose, Calif.) and washed. Afterwards, MSC were obtained as previously described (Villaron et al. 2004; Beyer and da Silva 2006). Briefly, low-density mononuclear cells (MNC) were isolated by Ficoll-Paque (Biochrom, Berlin, Germany) and plated at a cell density of 10^6 MNC/cm² on a plastic surface in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (Gibco BRL, Paisley, UK) containing 10% pre-selected fetal calf serum (FCS; BioWhittaker, Verviers, Belgium). Culture flasks were maintained in a humidified incubator at 37°C with 5% CO₂. Twice a week, adherent cells were fed by complete replacement of the medium, and non-adherent cells were subsequently washed out. When the layer was 80% confluent, the culture was trypsinized, and the cells were subcultured in two or three culture flasks (a "cell passage") at a cell density of 2.5×10^3 cells/m². Cells underwent three passages in culture in order to ensure that all contaminating hematopoietic cells had been totally washed out of the flask. Cell numbers obtained after each passage and the time taken to reach a 80% confluent layer were recorded in each comparative expansion. In six cases, expansion kinetics were further explored up to a fifth passage.

Flow cytometric immunophenotyping and cell cycle analysis

For the immunophenotypic characterization of MSC by flow cytometry from both sources, detached cells were washed and resuspended in PBS and then incubated with the following monoclonal antibodies directly conjugated with fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC), phycoerythrin (PE), phycoerythrin-Cyanin-5 (PCy5), peridinin-chlorophyll-protein (PerCP), or allophycocyanin (APC): CD90-FITC, CD14-FITC, CD73-PE, CD106-PE, CD166-PE, CD146-PE, HLA-DR-PerCP, CD45-PCy5, CD34-APC, and CD19-

APC (all from BDB), and CD105-FITC from InmunoStep (Salamanca, Spain). Isotype IgG control antibodies (BDB) were used in each case. Cells were then washed and acquired in a FACSCalibur flow cytometer (BDB). At least 10⁵ events were collected per sample.

Immunophenotypic

analysis was performed with the CellQuest and Paint-A-Gate Pro software (BDB; Villaron et al. 2004). For each antigen, the percentage of positive cells and the mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) ratio were calculated, the latter being the result of dividing the MFI value for a specific antigen by the MFI of the corresponding isotype control.

For cell cycle analysis, MSC were stained for nuclear

DNA content with propidium iodide by using the CycleTest DNA Reagent Kit (BDB) as previously described (San Miguel et al. 1996). Measurements were performed on a FACSCalibur flow cytometer (BDB) by using CellQuest software (BDB) and acquiring $\geq 20,000$ cells per sample. After cell doublets were excluded on a FL2-area/FL2-width dot plot by using the Paint-A-Gate Pro software (BDB), the proportion of cells in the different cell cycle

phases was calculated with the RFIT mathematical model included in the CellFit software (BDB).

CFU-F assay

Approximately 7.5×10^5 MNCs isolated from both sources were independently seeded in 25-cm² tissue culture flasks together with Iscove's modified Dulbecco's medium (IMDM; Gibco, Invitrogen, Paisely, UK) containing 12.5% FCS (Castro-Malaspina et al. 1980). The medium was changed every 3–4 days. After 14 days, flasks were washed with PBS, and the cells fixed with methanol, stained according to May-Grünwald-Giemsa (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), washed with distilled water, and mounted for optical microscopic analysis, which was performed on an Olympus BX41 microscope equipped with the Micro DP70 controller and manager software pack (Olympus Optical, Barcelona, Spain). Cell clusters containing more than 50 cells were scored as CFU-F colonies. Clonogenic efficiency was calculated as the number of colonies per 10^6 MNCs initially seeded.

Multilineage differentiation of MSC

In order to demonstrate the multilineage differentiation potential of the trabecular bone MSC (tbMSC), adipogenic, osteogenic, and chondrogenic differentiation was induced as previously described (Conget and Minguell 1999; Villaron et al. 2004; Beyer and da Silva 2006).

For osteogenic differentiation, fourth passage MSC were plated at 5×10^3 cells/cm² in a 9.6-cm² slideflask (Nunc, Denmark), grown up to 80% confluence, and incubated in osteogenic medium (NH Osteodiff Medium, Miltenyi Biotec, Germany). The medium was replaced every 3–4 days. After 10 days, cultures were washed with PBS and fixed in a solution of ice-cold 70% ethanol for 10 min. For alkaline phosphatase staining, slides were fixed in 100% methanol for 5 min, washed with PBS, and then incubated with 5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl phosphate/nitro blue tetrazolium (BCIP-NBT, Sigma-Aldrich) for 15–30 min, strictly following manufacturer's instructions.

For adipogenic induction, MSC from both sources were cultured in NH Adipodiff Medium (Miltenyi Biotec, Germany) under the same conditions (37°C with 5% CO₂) for 21 days. For Oil-red-O staining, slides were fixed 3.7% formaldehyde for 2 min, washed, and incubated with Oil-red-O (Merck) for 1 h at room temperature. A chamber slide that contained MSC growing in expansion medium (DMEM with 10% FCS, as previously described) without any differentiation cocktail was used as a control for osteogenic and adipogenic differentiation.

All sets of slides were washed with distilled water and mounted for optical microscopic analysis, which was performed on an Olympus BX41 microscope equipped with the Micro DP70 controller and manager software pack (Olympus Optical, Barcelona, Spain).

For chondrogenic differentiation, 5×10^5 cells were placed in a 15-ml polypropylene tube and centrifuged. The pellet was cultured at 37°C and 5% CO₂ in 500 μ l chondrogenic medium (NH Chondrodif Medium, Miltenyi Biotec, Germany), following the manufacturer's protocol. The medium was changed every 3–4 days. After 21 days of culture, pellets were embedded in paraffin, cut into 5-mm sections, and stained for aggrecan expression with a mouse anti-human aggrecan monoclonal antibody (Millipore Iberica, Spain) followed by incubation with a donkey anti-mouse antibody conjugated with Cy3 (Jackson Immunoresearch Europe, Suffolk, UK). Fluorescence microscopy analysis was performed on an Olympus Provis photo-microscope equipped with epifluorescence and the appropriate filter sets (Olympus Europe, Hamburg, Germany). Images were taken and digitalized with a DP-70 digital camera (Olympus Optical, Hamburg, Germany) attached to a computer running DP Controller v.1.2.1.108 and the DP Manager v.1.2.1.107 software (Olympus Optical).

In order to provide a quantitative comparative analysis of the differentiation ability of MSC from both sources, Image J software (freely available at <http://rsb.info.nih.gov/ij/>) was used to handle data from the same slides employed for the adipogenic, osteogenic, and chondrogenic differentiation tests and from the controls. Briefly, five images were randomly taken from each slide by using the 20 \times objective. These digital images were treated to balance the signal-to-noise ratio so that positive elements (Oil-Red-O droplets, alkaline-phosphatase staining, or aggrecan staining) were clearly distinguishable from the background. Following this, they were manually transformed into binary images in which only positive elements appeared as white pixels. Then, the percentage of the differentiation area was calculated as the white/black pixel ratio in the entire image, and the mean value for each slide was obtained.

Statistical analysis

SPSS version 15.0 software (Chicago, Ill.) was used for statistical analysis. For each variable, median and range, or mean \pm 2 standard errors of the mean (SEM) were calculated. To explore the differences in any variable between the iliac crest MSC and trabecular bone MSC, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U-test was used, whereas in order to explore the differences in any variable between MSC from both sources but within the same patient, the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks test was employed. Differences were considered to be statistically significant when P-values were <0.05 .

Results

Cellular yield and culture expansion data

The median cellular yield after grinding a femoral head was 4.0×10^6 cells (range: 0.34×10^6 to 17.85×10^6 cells) compared to 4.50×10^6 cells (range: 0.6×10^6 to 28×10^6 cells) from a 5ml to 10ml iliac crest aspiration from the same subjects. Median numbers of cells obtained through the various culture passages are shown in Fig. 1a.

The number of days to reach 80% confluence (i.e., the time to perform one cell passage in culture) shortened through the different passages, as would be expected, with no significant differences between the two sources in the first passages, but with a tendency to a significantly shorter time in later passages for MSC from trabecular bone compared with MSC from iliac crest (see Fig. 1b)

Flow cytometric immunophenotyping and cell-cycle analysis

Immunophenotypic assessment of MSC from trabecular bone (Fig. 2) demonstrated that they fulfilled general immunophenotypical criteria defining MSC, as stated by the ISCT (Dominici et al. 2006). In this regard, they were positive for CD90, CD73, CD105, and CD166, with faint positivity for CD106, whereas they were negative for the pan-hematopoietic marker CD45, the hematopoietic stem cell marker CD34, the pan-monocytic antigen CD14, the pan-B-cell marker CD19, and the class two HLA antigen HLA-DR. In addition, we also evaluated the expression of the novel osteoprogenitor marker CD146, which was positive in MSC from both cell sources. Interestingly, upon comparing the MFI ratio for each marker between iliac crest MSC and trabecular bone MSC, we observed that the CD90 MFI ratio was significantly higher in the latter group (87.8 ± 28 versus 52.6 ± 12 , $P=0.018$). No significant differences were seen in the MFI ratio for the remaining positive antigens between the MSC from the two sources.

Cell cycle analysis with PI staining showed that trabecular bone MSC, compared with iliac crest MSC from the same subject, displayed a slightly higher percentage of cells in S phase (0.8% versus 0.5%) and G2-M phases (3.06% versus 2.38%) of the cell cycle, although these differences were not statistically significant.

CFU-F content

After 14 days of CFU-F assay, the mean number of CFU-F colonies/106 seeded MSC was similar in the trabecular bone and the iliac crest group (11 ± 7.6 colonies versus 10.6 ± 7.5 colonies, respectively).

Osteogenic, adipogenic, and chondrogenic differentiation MSC obtained from trabecular bone and from iliac crest aspiration were able to differentiate in all cases into osteocytes, adipocytes, and chondrocytes (Fig. 3), another requirement, together with the immunophenotype, for fulfilling ISCT requirements for definition as MSC. No significant differences were seen between the two MSC sources with regard to differentiation ability, when the quantitative comparative analysis was performed. Thus, the mean percentage of the alkaline-phosphatase-positive area in the trabecular bone MSC group was 9.5 ± 2.1 , the percentage of Oil-Red-O droplets was 3.5 ± 1.7 , and the percentage of aggrecan-positive area in this group was 14.0 ± 6 . These values were 11.5 ± 4 , 2.9 ± 1.2 , and 12.2 ± 8 , respectively, in the iliac crest MSC group.

Discussion

The present work has, to the best of our knowledge, two main novel aspects. The first is that we have used a new method for obtaining MSC from femoral heads removed during hip replacement surgery. The method is based on the mechanical fragmentation of the whole femoral head and avoids the use of enzymatic digestion.

We have shown that cells obtained in this way fulfil ISCT criteria for the definition of MSC. The second is that we have compared the trabecular bone MSC with those obtained under standard conditions from BM aspiration from the iliac crest in the same subjects. This is important, since inter- individual variation may play a role when comparing the characteristics of the same cell type from different sources. We have shown that cells from the two origins are similar. This is a significant conclusion, since bone fragments from femoral heads are sometimes employed as a source of bone grafts, as a therapeutic tool (Farrell et al. 2005). Our results are in accordance with those obtained by Suva et al. (2004) who have analyzed the immunophenotypic and differentiation ability of MSC from femoral heads obtained from osteoarthritic patients, but by a different mechanical fragmentation from the one here described. Sakaguchi et al. (2004), when analyzing MSC obtained after collagenase digestion from the tibia in patients with knee osteoarthritis, have concluded that MSC from trabecular bone are almost identical to MSC obtained after aspirating BM from the tibia, although they have not made a comparison to standard iliac crest aspiration. Nevertheless, in a different study, MSC derived from 5 ml BM obtained from the proximal metaphyseal end of the femur during hip replacement in patients with non-traumatic osteonecrosis of the femoral head display an altered osteogenic and adipogenic ability compared with those from patients with osteoarthritis (Lee et al. 2006). Although we have not found any changes in the differentiation ability compared with MSC obtained from iliac crest in our series, none of our patients had osteonecrosis. Testing the differentiation ability of patients with osteonecrosis by our method (grinding the entire femoral head instead of taking a 5-ml BM sample from the medullar channel) would extend our knowledge concerning the alterations at the MSC level in this bone disorder, since a higher cell number of cells within the altered milieu of the femoral head would be analyzed. More recently, Rollin et al. (2008) have found, in an interesting study, that MSC from osteoarthritis (again aspirating BM cells from the femoral channel) display a different proteome and an increased chemotactic response compared with those of patients with hip fracture without osteoarthritis, but unfortunately they have not compared this with MSC obtained by standard iliac crest aspiration from the same subjects. The mild differences observed in our study between trabecular bone MSC from osteoarthritic patients and iliac crest MSC from the same patients, including the higher expression of the immature marker CD90, the lower expansion time through the different passages, and the higher percentage of cycling cells in the trabecular bone MSC, may be explained by differences at the gene expression or proteomic levels and therefore warrant further studies to explore this hypothesis. The expansion kinetics observed in both samples (Fig. 1) in the first three passages correspond mostly to the expansion of a mixed BM population, since total BM MNC were plated, whereas the kinetics from passage 3 onward are more representative of a pure MSC population (more than 97% of purity at this stage assessed by flow cytometry; data not shown). The percentage of FCS employed may also play a role in the expansion kinetics. We and others generally employ 10% FCS in the expansion media, but some groups are use 15% or 20% FCS, with an optimized growth and cellular yield (Sekiya et al. 2002). In summary, we have presented here a new method for the isolation of MSC from femoral heads of patients undergoing hip replacement surgery and have shown that cells obtained in this way fulfil standard criteria for the definition of MSC. An extensive comparison with MSC obtained from iliac crest aspiration of the same subjects has revealed that both cell types are similar in terms of expansion potential, immuno- phenotype, and multilineage differentiation ability. However, mild differences found between both MSC types warrant further studies (including gene expression or proteomic studies) to gain insight into the pathogenesis of osteoarthritis or similar disorders involving the femoral head.

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Figures

Fig. 1 Expansion data and growth kinetics of mesenchymal stromal cells (MSC). a) MSC culture expansion (N.S. not statistically significant). b) MSC growth kinetics

Fig. 2 Immunophenotypic profile of MSC from femoral head (a) and iliac crest (b).

Fig. 3 “In vitro” differentiation of MSC from femoral head and iliac crest. Osteogenic differentiation by alkaline phosphatase staining: MSC from femoral head (a), MSC from iliac crest (b), control c. Adipogenic differentiation by Oil-red-o stain- ing: MSC from femoral head (d), MSC from iliac crest (e), control (f). Chondrogenic differentiation by aggrecan immunofluorescence: MSC from femoral head (g), MSC from iliac crest (h), control (i). DAPI (4,6-diamidino-2-phyindole) nuclear staining: MSC from femoral head (j), MSC from iliac crest (k), control (l).

